

HEALTH, NUTRITION AND GENERAL CARE OF THE AGED IN ONDO WEST
LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF ONDO STATE

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ABSTRACT

Ageing is a process in which there is reduced capacity to replace worn-out tissues and cells resulting to changes in the health, nutrition and general wellbeing of a person. This study focused on the health, nutrition and general care of the aged in Ondo West Local Government Area (OWLGA) of Ondo State. Descriptive survey research design was used. The population for the study comprised of all 16,735 elders (60 years and above) in Ondo West Local Government Area of Ondo State. 17 males and 17 females all elderly, were selected from each of five wards in the LGA making 170 elders (1% of the population) using proportionate sampling technique. The research instrument was a structured and open-ended questionnaire. Data collected were analyzed using frequency count, mean and t-test. Findings revealed that (92.9%) of the elderly receive treatment for ailments; 53.5% had poor vision and 58.2% had stroke. Daily consumption of animal protein, tubers, legumes, fruits and vitamin A rich foods was low. There is a significant difference in self-reported ailments and dietary pattern among male and female elders. About three quarters (71.29%) of the respondents did not live alone and about three quarters (77.1%) claimed they had care givers. Based on the research findings, it was recommended that elders should be encouraged to make use of local nutritious foods to increase their consumption of animal protein, tubers, legumes fruits and vitamin A rich foods. They should also not be saddled with the responsibility of looking after grandchildren.

Keywords: Health, nutrition, dietary pattern, care, elders.

INTRODUCTION

Ageing is a process in which there is a reduced capacity to replace worn out cells. It is a continuous process that occurs throughout life cycle, resulting in procreative changes. Ageing in individuals is part of the total life process. Susceptibility to diseases increases with age, since there is a reduced capacity to handle physical stress (Harrick, 2002).

The World Health Organisation's definition of elderly is 'persons of 60 years of age or older (WHO, 2002). Aged people are growing in prevalence and their nutrition-related concerns impact upon health, function and life quality (McGee and Jensen, 2000). Changes in body composition, organs and system functions alter nutrient requirement and this nutritional challenges are more common in

aged persons than in younger adults. A nutritional challenge in an aged person is therefore a consequence of somatic, psychic or social problem. Typical causes of nutritional problems are chewing and swallowing disorders, cardiac insufficiency, depression, social deprivation and loneliness (Pirlich, Loch and Jensen, 2001).

Lack of fund to pay for adequate food can result in nutritional problems for the aged. There is reduction in energy requirement with increasing age, whereas there are increased requirement for a number of nutrients, such as: protein, riboflavin, Vitamin B6, calcium, Vitamin D and for some Vitamin B12. Therefore, since it is difficult for older people on relatively low-energy diets to meet their nutrients requirements from food, Vitamin supplements and fortified foods may be required to meet nutrient requirements. To ensure optimal nutritional status, one must assess nutritional requirement on an individual level and provide practical advice regarding appropriate choices which takes into account, physical and psychological conditions, body weight, level of physical activities, medication use, income, ethnics groups, social support, access to retail food outlets, cooking facilities and access to community support schemes.

It is a challenge for many aged people to maintain their interest in food, as there is a reduction in appetite with increasing age; therefore, it is important to keep aged people interested in food through the development of a variety of meals and snacks that are both nutritious and appetizing (Caryl, 2007). Certainly, taking Vitamins and supplements can help and a balanced diet plan is a must for aged people. Nutritious recipes for cooking can also help. Proper elderly nutrition and eating habit are crucial to maintain the quality of life, control blood sugar to avoid diabetes, maintain good vision, a positive mood, good sleep, energy, bone, muscle strength and digestion etc, these are affected by poor diets and thereby cause nutrition problems for the aged.

Studies in developed countries have indicated that among those aged 65years and above, malnutrition and obesity are common (USDA, 2002). The study noted that if elderly receive what is known as 'Nutritional Intervention', many diseases could be prevented. Intervention studies have indicated too that malnutrition is a major reason for hospitalization for the elderly (USDA, 2002).

As people grow older, they find out that they need more help with day-to -day tasks or healthcare. Aged people who live on their own are not able to get out and about as easily as they used to, they may also want extra company. Sometimes, the best way to receive help and support can be by living in an aged care home either on permanent basis or for a short stay called 'residential respite'. An aged person may need help because of an illness, a disability or an emergency. Staffs at aged care homes can help with day-to-day tasks (such as cleaning, cooking, laundry); personal care (such as dressing, grooming, going to the toilet) or 24hour nursing care (such as wound care, catheter care). Aged care system aims to make sure that all older people can receive support and quality care when they need it (Pirlich, Loch and Jensen, 2001).

Traditionally, aged care has been the responsibility of family members and was often provided within the extended family home in Africa. Increasingly in modern societies, aged care is now being provided by the State or charitable institutions. The reasons for this change are decreasing family size, the greater life expectancy of aged people, the geographical dispersion of families, and the tendency for women to be educated and work outside the home (Joseph, 2015).

It has been observed that most of the aged people usually have problems that are peculiar to them starting from age 60 and above, some diseases are common to elderly people as they age such as cardiovascular diseases, high blood pressure, heart diseases, stroke, osteoporosis and decrease in functions of the organs etc. Most of the elderly have challenges in care, usually they have no one to take proper care of them especially those living alone. Some of these aged people lack information

about their nutritional needs while others are illiterate and ignorant and all these may result in their untimely death. This research was therefore undertaken to identify the challenges in health, nutrition and general care of the aged in Ondo West Local Government Area in Ondo State (OWLGA). Specifically, the study determined:

- i. self reported ailments among the aged in OWLGA;
- ii. the dietary pattern of and frequency of consumption of major food group items by the aged in OWLGA;
- iii. whether adequate care was given to the aged in OWLGA;
- iv. the difference in the self reported ailments among male and female elderly in OWLGA; and
- v. the difference in the dietary pattern of male and female elderly in OWLGA.

Research questions

1. What are the self reported ailments among the aged in OWLGA?
2. What is the dietary pattern of and frequency of consumption of major food group items by the aged in OWLGA?
3. Are adequate care given to the aged in OWLGA?

Research hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in the self reported ailments of male and female elderly in OWLGA.
2. There is no significant difference in the dietary pattern of male and female elderly in OWLGA.

METHODOLOGY

The design used for this study was descriptive survey research design. The study was carried out in Ondo West Local Government Area of Ondo State. Ondo West Local Government Area is one of the 18 local government areas in Ondo State. There are 12 wards in the study area, they are: Bagbe/Igunsin, Igbado, Ilunla, Laje, Lekere, Newtown, Odojomu, Odosida, Okerowo, Okelisa, Surulere and Yaba. The headquarters of OWLGA is Ondo town and Ondo State is situated in the Western Region of Nigeria. Like other regions in the country, the area of study comprises of elderly with little or no attention in terms of care. They have been observed to be lacking in terms of care, have some ailments and poor nutrition this justifies the study in the area.

The population for the study comprised of all 16,735 elders (60 years and above) in Ondo West Local Government Area of Ondo State. [(National Population Commission (NPC), 2009), (Federal Republic of Nigeria Official Gazette, 2009)]. The sample size used for the study was 170 aged men and women in Ondo West Local Government Area. Proportionate sampling technique was used to determine the sample size. One percent of the total population was selected. Five wards were selected from the twelve wards in the Local Government Area by balloting. 17 males and 17 female elders were selected from each of the five wards. A well-structured questionnaire titled Dietary Pattern and Self-Reported Ailment Questionnaire containing 26 open ended questions was used to elicit information from the respondents. The instrument was divided into three sections (A-C). The questionnaire was validated by three experts in Food and Nutrition. Cronbach's alpha was used to determine the reliability of the questionnaire and a Cronbach's coefficient alpha of 0.80 was obtained. The validated copies of the questionnaire were administered to the selected elders through personal contact. The data collected was analyzed using frequency and simple percentages for the research questions while the hypotheses were analyzed using t-test at 0.05% level of significance.

RESULTS

Table 1: Self-reported ailments of the elderly in Ondo West Local Government Area

Self-reported ailments	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Rank
Swallowing problems	52	30.6	6 th
Cancer	21	12.4	13 th
Eye problem	34	20.0	10 th
Diabetes	28	16.5	11 th
Rheumatism	45	26.5	8 th
Hypertension	23	13.5	12 th
Arthritis	47	27.6	7 th
Tooth ache	67	39.4	4 th
Constipation	55	32.4	5 th
Waist pain	78	45.9	3 rd
Poor vision	91	53.5	2 nd
Stroke	99	58.2	1 st
Respiratory problem	43	25.3	9 th

Table 1 revealed the self-reported ailments of the elderly in OWLGA. It shows that (58.2%) reported stroke, 53.5% and 45.9% respectively reported poor vision and waist pain. About one third reported toothache, constipation and swallowing problems. Almost all (92.9%) of the respondents claimed to receive treatments for ailments. Majority of the respondents (87.6%, 83.5%, 89% and 79.4%) did not report cancer, diabetes, eye problem and hypertension respectively.

Table 2a revealed the dietary pattern of elderly in OWLGA. It shows that half (50%) of the respondents take three meals a day, 17.1% take a meal a day, two-thirds (65.3%) did not eat in between meals and half (51.8%) did not skip meals. Half (55.3%) take fruits daily. Half (59.4%) take vegetables once daily. All respondents (100%) take onions and tomatoes. About two-thirds (66.5%) do not take snacks. Half (56.5%) buy cooked foods from vendors.

Table 2b shows the frequency of consumption of major food groups by the elderly. Daily consumption of animal protein (20%), tubers (41.8%), legumes (22.4%), fruits (40.6%) and vitamin A rich foods (30%) were low.

Table 2a: Dietary pattern of the Elderly in Ondo West Local Government Area

	Yes	%	No	%
Daily consumption of food				
Once	29	17.05	141	82.90
Twice	53	31.20	117	68.80
Thrice	85	50.00	85	50.0
More than thrice	3	2.14	167	98.20
Eating in-between meals	59	34.71	111	65.29
Skipping meals	82	48.20	88	51.80
If yes, state the meals you skip				
Breakfast	33	19.41	137	80.59
Lunch	58	34.12	112	65.88
Supper	79	46.47	91	53.53
Daily consumption of fruits				
Fruits taken	94	55.30	76	44.70
Orange	43	25.29	127	74.71
Water melon	76	44.71	94	55.29
Guava	12	7.06	158	92.94
Apple	98	57.64	72	42.35
Pineapple	65	38.23	105	61.77
Cherry	23	13.53	147	86.47
Daily consumption of vegetables				
Once	101	59.41	69	40.59
Twice	69	40.59	101	59.41
Types of vegetables consumed				
Carrot	67	39.41	103	60.59
Cucumber	34	20.00	136	80.00
Cabbage	22	12.94	148	87.06
Spinach	43	25.29	127	74.71
Lettuce	37	21.76	133	78.24
Onions	170	100.00	0	0.00
Tomatoes	170	100.00	0	0.00
Taking snacks				
Buying cooked foods from vendors	57	33.50	113	66.50
Frequency of purchase				
Everyday	96	56.50	74	43.50
Frequently	45	26.47	125	73.53
Occasionally	67	39.41	103	60.59
	58	34.12	112	65.88

Table 2b: Food frequency questionnaire

FOOD LIST	Once/day	%	1-3times/wk	%	4-6times/wk	%	Less than once /wk or never	%
Animal protein (meat, fish, egg)	34	20.00	51	30.00	74	43.53	11	6.47
Tubers/Roots (cassava, yam)	71	41.77	35	20.59	38	22.35	26	15.29
Legumes (beans, groundnut etc)	38	22.35	49	28.82	81	47.65	2	1.18
Cereals (maize, rice etc)	84	49.41	66	38.82	17	10.00	3	1.77
Fruits	69	40.59	83	48.82	17	10.00	1	0.59
Milk and Milk Products	102	60.00	54	31.76	11	6.47	0	0.00
Green vegetables	88	51.76	76	44.70	8	4.71	2	1.18
Vit. A rich foods (liver, carrots, etc)	51	30.00	63	37.06	36	21.80	20	11.76

Table 3: Adequacy of Care of the Elderly in Ondo West Local Government Area

Adequacy of Care	Yes	Percentage	No	Percentage
Living alone	49	28.80	121	71.20
Adult children far away	51	30.00	119	70.00
Meal Preparation (Self)	18	10.59	152	89.41
Grandchild/children	41	21.18	129	75.82
Child/children	12	7.06	158	92.94
Care giver	51	30.00	119	70.00
Relative(s)	46	27.06	124	72.94
Neighbour(s)	2	1.18	168	98.82
Presence of regular care giver	131	77.10	39	22.90
Care for grandchildren	125	73.50	45	26.50
Living with grandchild/children	101	59.40	69	40.60

Table 3 shows that 28.8% of the respondents live alone and 30% have their adult children far from them. Caregiver prepares meals for 30% of the respondents. About three quarters (73.5%) still look after their grandchildren.

Table 4: Self-reported ailments among male and female elderly in Ondo West Local Government Area

Sex	Number	Mean	Std. Deviation	df	t-cal	t-crit	Remark
Male	76	14.80	2.26	118	18.41	1.95	Significant
Female	94	21.95	3.70				

Table 4 revealed the self-reported ailments of male and female elderly in OWLGA. It shows that the t-calculated is (18.41) while t-table value is (1.96). The t-calculated is greater than the t-table value. This implies that there is significant difference in the self-reported ailments among male and female elderly in Ondo West Local Government Area. Females reported more ailments than males.

Table 5: Dietary pattern of male and female elderly in Ondo West Local Government Area.

Sex	Number	Mean	Std. Deviation	df	t-cal	t-crit	Remark
Male	76	10.05	2.258	118	14.256	1.95	Significant
Female	94	9.75	3.058				

Table 5 shows that the t-calculated is (14.256) while t-table value is (1.96). The t-calculated is greater than the t-table value. This implies that there is significant difference in the dietary pattern of male and female elderly in Ondo West Local Government Area. Males had better dietary pattern than females.

Discussion of findings

Findings of this study reveal that a number of elders in Ondo West Local Government Area of Ondo State reported suffering from stroke (58.2%), poor vision (53.5%), waist pain (45.9%), toothache (39.4%), constipation (32.4%), swallowing problems (30.6%), arthritis (27.6%) and respiratory problems (25.3%). All ailments in this study are common ailments of the elderly throughout the world. Previous studies had similar reports. Fadupin (2012) reported that many (52.7%) of the Ibadan elders that were studied complained of poor health due to joint pain, poor vision, constipation and hypertension. Adebimpe, Omobuwa, Omisore and Adeoye (2014) in their study of elderly women in Osun State reported that (66.3%) of their respondents had complaints of joint pains (Awoka as expressed in the local language). Olarewaju (2015) also reported musculoskeletal (rheumatism, cramps) eye problems, respiratory problems, high blood pressure, cough, toothache, other problems (sickle cell anaemia, cancer and epilepsy) alimentary/digestive problems and diabetes among elders in Ondo State.

The eye problems observed in this study could be as a result of age-related macular degeneration (AMD). According to National Eye Institute (NEI) (2015) age-related macular degeneration (AMD) is a leading cause of vision loss in Americans aged 60 and older, affecting an estimated 10 million people. The aged people are more likely to lack proper hydration in warm-weather months and during illness. Medications and chronic medical conditions often increase the risk of dehydration. Mild to moderate complications from dehydration include constipation, headache, dizziness, low blood pressure, rapid heartbeat and loss of consciousness.

During the investigation, it was observed that 50% of the respondents take three meals a day, about one-quarter (17.05%) a meal per day, about two-thirds (65.3%) did not eat in between meals, half did not skip meals and two thirds did not take snacks. Olasunbo and Ayo (2013) reported that two thirds and almost all their respondents in Ile-Ife ate three meals per day and had favourite foods respectively. Olarewaju (2015) observed that very few elders in the study ate between meals and avoided certain foods. Two thirds of respondents (63%) in Olasunbo and Ayo (2013) study also ate thrice daily, 35% skipped meals, 19% drank alcohol and 4.5% were smokers. Afolabi, Olayiwola, Sanni and Oyawoye (2012) reported that the elders in their study (South West Nigeria) ate three meals per day; snacks or between meals were not common.

The study further showed that daily consumption of animal protein, tubers, legumes, fruits and Vitamin A rich foods were low. In a similar study Olarewaju (2015) found out that daily consumption of all nutrients by elders except animal protein was generally low. Elders in the study (Ondo State) had diets high in animal protein, moderate in tubers, legumes, cereals and green vegetables but low in fruits, diary and vitamin A rich foods.

This study showed that the respondents have regular care givers but look after their grandchildren. Caregivers prepare meals for most of them. Previous studies revealed that elders who still have young children or grandchildren to cater for have greater vulnerability to poor well-being than those living alone and that diversion of care to meeting the needs of their young children can have negative impact on the health of the elderly (Okumagba, 2011; Adebowale, Atte and Ayeni, 2012). This study further showed that self reported ailments were higher among females than males and dietary pattern was better among males than females. This is logical because better nutrition is expected to lead to less occurrence of ailments and diseases.

CONCLUSION

Self reported ailments among elderly in Ondo town were stroke, poor vision, waist pain, toothache, constipation, swallowing problems, arthritis and respiratory problems. Most of these health problems are associated with aging; however, some of them could be prevented or managed. Most of

these ailments will reduce intake of nutrients and predispose them to other diseases. Majority of elderly in Ondo town take at least three meals per day while few of them (about one-quarter) consumed a meal per day. Eating in between meals and skipping meals were not common among elderly in this area. Daily consumption of animal protein, tubers, legumes, fruits and vitamin A rich foods were low. If foods containing these nutrients are consumed daily elders will be healthier and able to meet RDA. The low consumption in vitamin A rich foods could be responsible for the poor vision observed in the elders. The availability and quality of health care made available by children, care givers, grandchildren are vital for the general well-being of aged people.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

- I. Ailments reported in this study are common ones with elders throughout the world. Elders in the study area should report any noticed ailments in the nearest hospital for proper treatment
- ii. Elders should be encouraged to eat healthy snacks (especially fruits) in-between meals and avoid skipping meals to be able to meet the RDA
- iii. Workshops, seminars and nutrition education programmes should be organised to encourage elders to make use of cheap local nutritious (different forms and types of fishes, crayfish, yam, beans, fruits available at various seasons, tomatoes carrots etc) to increase their consumption of animal protein, tubers, legumes, fruits and vitamin A rich foods (that were poorly consumed in this study)
- iv. Elders should not be saddled with the responsibility of looking after grandchildren. They should not be left alone to provide for their daily or nutritional needs, members of the family should endeavour to provide their needs and rally round them at all times.

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